

History-enhanced ICT for Sustainability Education

History Resources and Links v1.0

These resources accompany the videos recorded by University of the West of England Historians for each week of the module Sustainable Business and Computing (UFCFLM-15-3) as part of the BSc Business Computing degree. The topic of each week was selected to be relevant to the content of the module that week.

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Week / Topic	Resources and Links
1. Introduction: History & Sustainability	Live, in-class introduction. No additional Resources.
2. Dirty Business: Limited Companies and Corporations	<p><u>Article</u> Dalrymple, W. (2019) 'Lessons for capitalism from the East India Company', Financial Times, 30 August</p> <p><u>Podcasts</u> Dr. Philip J. Stern on The Corporations that built British Colonialism (58 mins) https://open.spotify.com/episode/2i4TOtwe2lvSVarMNVXD8N Anita Anand and William Dalrymple - Empire podcast. Series 1 is all about East India Company and British Empire in South Asia. https://open.spotify.com/show/0sBh58hSTReUQiK4axYUVx</p> <p><u>Book</u> Dalrymple, W. (2020) <i>The Anarchy: The Relentless Rise of the East India Company</i>. 1st edition. London: Bloomsbury Publishing Plc</p>
3. The Atlantic Economy and Abolition.	<p><u>Articles</u> Short article overviewing Bristol's involvement with the slave trade: https://www.blackhistorymonth.org.uk/article/section/history-of-slavery/bristol-and-the-transatlantic-slave-trad/ Longer-ish article on abolition: https://aeon.co/essays/the-british-empire-was-built-on-slavery-then-grew-by-antislavery</p> <p><u>Datasets</u> Trans-Atlantic Slave Voyages database: https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database See the slave ships departures and arrivals. Legacies of British Slavery database: https://www.ucl.ac.uk/lbs/ Find out who was compensated by the British Government when slavery was abolished. e.g. search on Bristol. Also shows what industries some of this compensation flowed to.</p>
4. Dirty Cities: Pollution and the Urban Environment	<p><u>Podcasts</u> A short interview with Lee Jackson, author of <i>Dirty Old London: The Victorian Fight Against Filth</i>.</p>

	<p>https://www.npr.org/2015/03/12/392332431/dirty-old-london-a-history-of-the-victorians-infamous-filth</p> <p>In Our Time: Booth's Life and Labour Survey. Melvyn Bragg and guests discuss Charles Booth's survey, <i>The Life and Labour of the People in London</i>, published in 17 volumes from 1889 to 1903. Booth (1840-1916), a Liverpoolian shipping line owner, surveyed every household in London to see if it was true, as claimed, that as many as a quarter lived in poverty. He found that it was closer to a third, and that many of these were either children with no means of support or older people no longer well enough to work. He went on to campaign for an old age pension, and broadened the impact of his findings by publishing enhanced Ordnance Survey maps with the streets coloured according to the wealth of those who lived there. https://www.bbc.co.uk/sounds/play/m000wsxf</p> <p><u>Resource</u></p> <p>Charles Booth's Poverty Maps. Between 1886 and 1903, social reformer Charles Booth led an investigation into the life and labour of people in London. Here you can look at an interactive version of the famous maps produced by Booth (and compare it to contemporary London). The digital archive also comprises over 450 volumes of interviews, questionnaires, observations and statistical information. It documents the social and economic life of London, highlighting all of its contrasts, complexities and contradictions. The archive also takes us "behind the scenes" of the Inquiry itself, showing how Booth and his research team developed new methodologies and techniques in what is now recognised as a key milestone in the development of social research techniques. https://booth.lse.ac.uk/map/14/-0.1174/51.5064/100/0</p>
5. Slumming It: 'Improving' the Urban Environment	<p><u>Resource</u></p> <p>Exploring the slum: a digital exhibition and resource made by students at the University of Derby https://slumexplorers.wordpress.com/</p> <p><u>Book</u></p> <p>Koven, S. (2004) <i>Slumming : sexual and social politics in Victorian London</i>. Princeton, N.J. ; Princeton University Press.</p> <p><u>Primary sources</u></p> <p>A SANITARY REMONSTRANCE. The Times, 5 July 1849. James Greenwood, The Seven Curses of London (1869). Gustave Doré., 'Wentworth Street, Whitechapel' (1872). CRUELTY TO CHILDREN – A REVOLTING CASE IN HUNGATE. York Herald, 24 October 1896. Rowntree, Poverty: A Study of Town Life (1901), p. 5. Medical officer of health reports on the Hungate district, 1906-7. York City Archives. Image of Bell Street, Leeds, 1901. Extract from Oral history interview with Rene Sheard, born 1911, York Oral History Project. Extract from Oral history interview with Nell Fearn, who grew up in Hungate – a poor working class district of York – in the early twentieth century. York Health Department, Chief Medical Officers' Report, 1914.</p>

6. Women, children and sweated labour. The Match Girls' Strike, 1888	<p><u>Primary sources</u> Besant, Annie. Rosewater for the plague. The Link. 23 June 1888 <u>Resource</u> The Match Workers Strike Fund Register. TUC History Online. http://www.unionhistory.info/matchworkers/matchworkers.php</p>
7. Silent Spring: The Rise of Environmentalism	<p><u>Book</u> Carson (1963) <i>Silent spring</i>. London: Hamish Hamilton. <u>Resource</u> Images from Earth Day 1970 Documentary - A Fierce Green Fire: The Battle for a Living Planet. https://www.afiercegreenfire.com/about/</p>
8. Make do and Mend	No additional content
9. The Medical Revolution	<p><u>Book</u> Porter, Roy. (2003) <i>Flesh in the age of reason</i>. London: Allen Lane. <u>Paper</u> Jones, C. (1996) <i>The Great Chain of Buying: Medical Advertisement, the Bourgeois Public Sphere, and the Origins of the French Revolution</i>. The American historical review. [Online] 101 (1), 13–40.</p>
10. The Nuclear Age	<p><u>Journal Issues</u> <i>Social and cultural histories of British nuclear mobilisation since 1945</i>. Contemporary British History, Volume 33, Issue 2 (2019) <i>British Nuclear Culture</i>. The British Journal for the History of Science 45 no. 4 (2012) <u>Film</u> Kubrick, S. (1963) <i>Dr. Strangelove</i>.</p>